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Sustainable Urban Design and People's Perceptions

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Abstract: The idea of ‘Sustainable Urban Design’ has become increasingly popular in recent years as urbanization quickens and technology transforms our communities. This concept explores how urban spaces can be planned, developed, and managed to enhance ecological resilience, improve quality of life, and promote social equity. People, being major components of these spaces, play a major role in shaping the nature of urban through their activities and behavioural approach towards it. Therefore, understanding people’s perception towards the urban design around them is an effective method to comprehend their behavioural reception to the concept of sustainable urban design and its impact on their lifestyle. In this context, the study aims to: (1) conduct a comparative analysis of sustainable urban design practices—both traditional and modern—in three global urban centres; (2) assess the applicability and viability of these practices within the city of Delhi, India; and (3) explore residents’ perceptions of the practicality and impact of these designs. Ultimately, the paper seeks to provide a comprehensive assessment of how smart urban designs and planning can be effectively utilised to foster sustainability.

Keywords: *sustainable urban design; urban planning; ecological resilience; comparative urban analysis; resident perception; sustainability practices*

Main highlights:

- The paper explores sustainable urban design through global examples of 3 different regions – Singapore, Masdar City (UAE) and Copenhagen (Denmark).
- Findings from these examples are taken and their practicality analysed in terms of case study of Delhi, India.
- Survey shows that Delhi residents are cautiously optimistic about the applicability of these practices.
- People identified clean air, green spaces, waste management, and heat-resilient infrastructure as top priorities.
- The study concludes that sustainable urban design must integrate citizen engagement with ecological and governance solutions to be effective.

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1. Introduction

Urban design is a dynamic, multidimensional process that shapes the form and function of cities. Unlike static planning, it evolves continuously with geography, culture, technology, and socio-economic transformations. In recent years, sustainable urban design has emerged as a pressing global concern, as cities face challenges such as environmental degradation, climate vulnerability, and rising social inequalities. At its core, sustainable design seeks to balance development with ecological preservation, ensuring cities remain liveable and resilient for current and future generations.

The urgency of adopting sustainable urban practices is underscored by global frameworks such as the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities. This goal emphasizes inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable urban spaces, recognizing that over half of the world's population now lives in cities, a figure projected to rise to 68% by 2050 (UN, 2019).

Yet, urban design is not simply about infrastructure-it is deeply tied to people. Citizens are the primary users of urban spaces, and their activities, behaviours, and perceptions directly influence the success of sustainable design interventions. For instance, building pedestrian-friendly roads only works if residents find them safe and accessible; waste segregation succeeds when communities actively participate. Thus, studying people's perceptions of sustainable design is as crucial as analysing its technical features.

This research paper explores sustainable urban design in two ways: first, by reviewing successful practices from cities worldwide, and second, by analysing the perceptions of the residents of Delhi regarding its applicability and practicality. Drawing insights from Singapore's Smart Nation initiative, Masdar's zero-carbon design, and Copenhagen's cycling culture, the study provides a comparative backdrop for Delhi, a megacity grappling with pollution, congestion, and rapid urban growth. The survey results shed light on residents' awareness, challenges, and expectations, forming the basis for recommendations tailored to Delhi's context.

2. Literature Review & Global Context

2.1 Sustainable Urban Design: Conceptual Overview

Sustainable urban design refers to the planning, development, and management of urban spaces in ways that balance environmental sustainability, social well-being, and economic viability. Unlike traditional urban planning, which often prioritized industrial growth and mobility, sustainable design emphasizes ecological resilience, energy efficiency, inclusive spaces, and community engagement. It emphasizes designing spaces that not only meet present needs but also safeguard opportunities for future generations, aligning closely with the philosophy of sustainable development (Brundtland Report, 1987). Globally, cities have experimented with both high-tech "smart" solutions and traditional design principles, creating a diverse spectrum of approaches.

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In Meijer and Bolívar's (2016) analysis of 51 papers on smart cities, they theorize three different ideal-typical definitions and categorizations of smart cities: (i) *Technological focus* — which means smart cities use smart technologies through which all the other problems in the city are refracted; (ii) *Human resource focus* — smart cities are homes to smart people, where there exists an upward, multiplier effect between smart infrastructure, smart businesses and smart citizens; and ultimately (iii) *Governance focus* — a streamlined approach to governance and government–citizen interactions.

The study argues that crises can act as catalysts for innovation, pushing cities to adopt more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable practices. A major emphasis is on the role of governance and citizen participation, as top-down measures alone are insufficient to ensure sustainable and equitable outcomes. The pandemic has created both disruptions and opportunities for cities. (Abbate et al., 2019). By learning from these experiences, urban planners and policymakers can steer transitions towards more sustainable, equitable, and resilient urban futures.

Importantly, sustainable urban design is dynamic and context-dependent. The approach varies across regions based on geography, culture, and governance. For instance, a compact, walkable city may be ideal for European contexts but challenging in sprawling South Asian megacities unless complemented by efficient transit systems. Similarly, cultural traditions, such as courtyard housing in South Asia or cycling culture in Northern Europe, shape how sustainability is perceived and practiced.

Another key aspect is the role of people's perceptions and behaviours. Sustainable design cannot succeed if citizens do not use, maintain, or support the infrastructures provided. For example, the success of a cycling network depends not only on infrastructure but also on whether people feel safe, socially encouraged, and culturally inclined to cycle. Thus, urban design is both a physical and a social project.

The next section reviews three notable cases—Singapore, Masdar (UAE), and Copenhagen—that provide valuable lessons for Delhi. Each case study was carefully selected based on the following criteria. Namely, the project:

- Can be replicated by other cities, within each city's context
- Is self-sustaining and has successfully progressed from a pilot to a scaling stage
- Identifies costs and benefits clearly, and those that can be monetized
- Is a disruptive solution with a clear outcome.

2.2 Singapore

Southeast Asia has a variety of urban manifestations (Figure 1): three megacities (Bangkok, Jakarta, and Manila) with populations in excess of ten million; a city state (Singapore); three countries (Brunei, Malaysia, the Philippines) with over 50 per cent of the population living in urban areas; and seven with predominantly rural populations, namely, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Myanmar, Thailand, Timor Leste, and Vietnam (Population Reference Bureau, 2009).

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Figure 1: Populations in Southeast Asian major cities, J. Philippines (2015)

Singapore, as a city-state, has consistently ranked highly in different smart city measurements and indices. For instance, Singapore was named “2023 Smart City” by Swiss business school Institute for Management Development (IMD), which ranks 141 cities by how they use technology to address the challenges they face to achieve a higher quality of life.

The success of Singapore as a smart city is embedded in its unique geographical, technological and policy landscape. Singapore has established itself as a global model of sustainable and technologically integrated urbanism. Less than a century ago, Singapore was a small swamp-filled island on the southernmost tip of continental Asia. In a span of less than 50 years, the city-state has transformed into a major global commerce, financial and transportation hub.

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Figure 2: Rapid Urbanization in Singapore, World Bank, 2018

Many factors have come into play over the years to make Singapore the “Smart Island Nation” that it is today. The reforms led by the government emphasize the integration of digital technologies, data-driven governance, and urban design to improve mobility, housing, and resource management. Each reform (Figure 3) gradually integrated technology into the urban fabric, strengthening infrastructure, connectivity, and governance systems to support rapid urban growth.

Figure 3: Timeline of Reforms in ICT sector of Singapore

Among these, the Smart Nation Initiative launched in 2014 marked a turning point, positioning technology at the core of urban development. The vision was to improve people’s lives and create more opportunities through ICT. The three priority areas, underpinned by cyber security, were: (i) Elderly (ii) Transportation and (iii) Data. The smart nation initiative was a whole-of-nation approach to enhance the quality of living for the country. (IMDA Singapore, 2014). One

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of the key areas of the initiative was the sharing of government data to the public to encourage co-creation of solutions. At present, urban planning is carried out at two levels—the concept plan, which is a macro-level blueprint, and the statutory master plan, which translates the concept plan into one with greater detail (Ooi, 2004). The concept plans are frequently revised (usually once every five years) to address the changing needs of Singapore, such as that of a “tropical city of excellence” in 1991 and that of a “thriving world-class city” in 2001 (Urban Redevelopment Authority, 2018).

Singapore highlights how governance capacity and planning foresight are crucial for successful sustainable design and inspires other smart cities to do follow its lead.

2.3 Masdar City, UAE

Countries in the Middle East have been remarkably proactive in developing smart cities, with a tendency to build them from the ground up rather than incorporating technology into existing environments. Saudi Arabia stands out especially for its ambitious giga-projects. It is currently developing four significant smart cities—NEOM, Amaala, Qiddiya and the Red Sea Project—each involving multibillion-dollar construction contracts. Masdar City, near Abu Dhabi, was envisioned as one of the world’s first zero-carbon cities. Although its ambitious targets have been scaled down, Masdar remains a fascinating experiment in blending modern technology with traditional design.

This is a remarkably unique zone for the study of urbanism as the shared heritage, traditional urban form, and socioeconomic conditions offer homogeneity but at the same time there is inequality in distribution of the wealth derived from the rich natural oil resources. There are also constant population fluctuations due to regional conflicts and immigrations.

Figure 4: Total Urban Population of MECA countries in 2019 (Reza et. al, 2021)

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Masdar demonstrates how cultural traditions can complement modern sustainability practices, a lesson Delhi could integrate given its rich architectural legacy. Masdar's smart city solutions are developed in a collaboration of government, private companies, universities and individuals. The city offers citizens excellent opportunities in education, mobility, and recreation. It shows the role of local government in not only investing in "visible infrastructure" but also channelling their limited powers towards the development of the "invisible infrastructure" – the institutions, incentives and signals that govern the lives of people. Masdar City combines traditional Arabic architectural techniques with advanced technology to create a cool and pedestrian-friendly environment where people live, work, learn and play. The student residences for the Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence (Figure 5) are defined by the terracotta-coloured, undulating glass-reinforced concrete balcony 'screens' that serve the same role as traditional Arabic mashrabiya screens.

Figure 5: Student residences for the Mohamed Bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence

Starting from scratch shows some interesting advantages in smart urban planning as you can aim high. These infrastructural changes have the potential for remarkable transformation that goes far beyond bricks and mortar. Zero-emission and zero waste are very realistic objectives for Masdar. It is formed on the belief that a 'responsible' producer of oil can support the transformation towards renewable energy. The urban development of Masdar is not only based on environmental sustainability; the social and economic structures are also considered.

There are many contemporary examples where this has been practiced: In Jordan, Amman provides a hopeful and refreshing model for the region. With the "Greater Amman Master Plan," which earned the city the 2007 World Leadership Award for Town Planning, Amman's Master Plan is the first forward-looking, comprehensive city-planning strategy in the region. NEOM is set to be one of the most innovative cities in the world - by automating the city and introducing a car-free transportation system, powered by renewable energy. The Smart Dubai Happiness Meter is a simple yet very powerful live sentiment capture tool, implemented to measure happiness among city experiences across thousands of touchpoints. This plan focuses on several aspects of urban development such as better public transportation, green and pedestrian-only spaces and youth recreational areas. This region serves as an example to the

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rest of the globe of how governments may use policy reform to improve the lives of people both inside and outside the country's boundaries.

2.4 Copenhagen, Denmark

The concept of sustainability has been present in Europe for centuries, although not always explicitly defined as such. In medieval times, practices such as crop rotation and the use of natural fertilizers were common, contributing to the longevity of agricultural systems. The Industrial Revolution shifted towards more intensive and extractive forms of production, which led to environmental degradation and social inequality. It was not until the 20th century that sustainability began to emerge as a distinct concept, with the publication of the Club of Rome's Limits to Growth report.

Today, Europe is at the forefront of sustainability efforts, with policies and initiatives focused on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting renewable energy, and protecting biodiversity. Nordic countries, specifically, are global leaders in urban sustainability due to their commitment to innovative policies, collaborative initiatives, and strong welfare models that prioritize quality of life and environmental well-being. Copenhagen consistently ranks among the most sustainable cities globally and has a long-standing tradition of pursuing green solutions. Back in 1972, oil accounted for 92 per cent of gross energy consumption in Denmark (Figure 6), however, with the oil crisis came new initiatives, and in 1978 the first major wind turbine started generating electricity in Denmark. In 2022, solar and wind energy generated 59.3% of Denmark's electricity consumption (The Copenhagen Post). 98% of all households in Copenhagen are today connected to a district heating system. Denmark aims to be the world's first country entirely independent of fossil fuels by 2050 (IEA, 2023). Since 2015, Copenhagen has been ranked the world's most bicycle-friendly city several times, the latest in 2021. In 2022, Copenhagen invested 10 million Euros in cycling infrastructure in order to maintain and improve its position as the most bicycle-friendly city in the world. This has resulted not only in reduced congestion but has also caused the carbon emissions to dip significantly.

Copenhagen Population

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Copenhagen Carbon Emissions

Figure 6: Population and Carbon Emission Statistics in Copenhagen, 2019

Copenhagen is a city where growth and prosperity go hand in hand, but there are also challenges: growth results in the need to create space for more people, more jobs and more mobility. The new district of Nordhavn will provide some of the answers to these challenges. The development of Nordhavn will help to counteract the tendency to increase the levels of displacement in the region, through the creation of new homes and work centres.

Thus, cities can only be understood as smart when they are first understood as living breathing organisms that evolve with the changing environment and the changing time. Sustainability cannot come into play in an ecosystem without the people consciously and willingly choosing it at every step in their daily routines - be it taking the electronic bus or carpooling instead of driving personal vehicles or an office opting for solar power as their source of energy. It is only then that the cities will indeed become "smart" and act, adapt, and synchronize with the development happening. Together, these cases form the preliminary ground for assessing people's perceptions of Delhi's own urban design, explored in the next sections.

3. Case Study: People's Perceptions of Sustainable Urban Design in Delhi

Following the global overview of sustainable urban design practices, it is essential to situate the discussion within the lived realities of a rapidly urbanizing city. Delhi provides a critical case, as it represents both the challenges and opportunities of sustainability in the Global South: rapid population growth, air pollution, infrastructure pressures, and rising climate vulnerabilities. To understand how sustainability is being received and interpreted at the community level, a survey was conducted among Delhi residents, focusing on their familiarity with sustainable urban design, perceptions of practicality, and the everyday impacts of initiatives implemented so far.

The survey was conducted online and targeted residents across Delhi's 11 districts, including individuals who had lived in the city for periods ranging from six months to ten years. It also incorporated responses from temporary visitors, offering valuable insights from a tourist's perspective. The responses reflect a growing public consciousness of sustainability. Nearly 90%

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of respondents reported having observed some form of sustainable initiative in the city, highlighting that interventions are present in the urban landscape and noticed by citizens.

Figure 7: Duration of residence in Delhi of respondents

When asked to rate Delhi’s current urban design on sustainability-related dimensions (green space, walkability, public transport quality, waste management, and air quality), the mean ratings stood at 3.29/5, suggesting a middling experience. Overall, 68% rated Delhi’s sustainability performance as “poor” or “average”, reflecting widespread concern about environmental and infrastructural deficits. This provides impetus for initiating more and more sustainable urban plans for development of the city.

Figure 8: Quality of Urban Spaces in Delhi as per respondents (1-Very poor to 5-Excellent)

Respondents were asked whether sustainable urban design measures (e.g., cycle lanes, community composting, cool roofs, more parks, EV public buses) are practical in Delhi’s context. Only 24.6% believed such measures were somewhat practical, and identified major barriers as: space constraints (51.2%), governance & policy gaps (75.6%) cost concerns (65.9%), and public behaviour/awareness (56.1%).

About 24.1% of respondents reported that existing sustainable initiatives (e.g., metro expansions, tree-planting drives, e-rickshaw penetration) had positively affected their daily

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lives — notably in commuting time reduction, comfort during summer (cooling measures), and access to public green spaces. However, 17.3% reported no noticeable improvement, citing poor accessibility or uneven distribution across neighbourhoods (central & south Delhi vs. peripheries).

Which sustainable features did you observe (if any)?

Figure 9: Sustainable Design initiatives in Delhi

The lived impacts of these initiatives remain uneven. Only 24.4% of residents reported that sustainability measures have significantly improved their daily life, though a larger share observed at least some improvement. Importantly, willingness to engage in sustainable practices is high: nearly 78% of respondents expressed a definite willingness to support measures such as waste reduction, tree planting, or the use of public transport.

Have sustainable initiatives (e.g., green drives, pedestrian zones, electric buses) improved your daily life in Delhi?

Figure 10: Impact of sustainable design initiatives on respondents

Residents identified the most urgent needs for Delhi's urban future: pollution control, expansion of green spaces, effective waste management, and heat-resilient infrastructure. At the same time, they highlighted persistent challenges such as inadequate maintenance, weak enforcement, limited policy funding, and low levels of awareness. These findings underscore

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that sustainable urban design in Delhi must go beyond the introduction of infrastructure to ensure inclusivity, operational efficiency, and long-term maintenance.

Residents of Delhi show growing awareness and conditional optimism about sustainable urban design but are pragmatic about feasibility. The clear public priorities are better transport, increased green space, and robust waste systems — interventions that directly improve day-to-day life. Effective implementation will require stronger governance, equitable distribution of benefits, and sustained community engagement.

Conclusion

This study shows that sustainable urban design is not just a technical goal but a real necessity—and increasingly, a shared expectation—among people living in cities like Delhi. From the global examples of Copenhagen and Singapore, we see how clean energy, better transport, and people-friendly planning can make cities more liveable and environmentally resilient. At the same time, our survey in Delhi reveals a more nuanced picture: while many residents are aware of and open to sustainable design, they remain wary of challenges such as poor maintenance, weak enforcement, and governance gaps.

What comes through strongly is that people in Delhi see their most urgent needs in very practical terms: cleaner air, more green spaces, reliable waste management, and infrastructure that can withstand rising heat. Some initiatives are already making a difference in daily life, and encouragingly, a large majority of respondents expressed willingness to support sustainability efforts themselves. This shows that beyond policies and technologies, Delhi has the people-power and community readiness to move the agenda forward.

The bigger message here is that sustainable urban design only works when it connects with lived experiences. It must go beyond blueprints to ensure that communities are part of shaping and sustaining it. By combining ecological care with social fairness and stronger institutions, Delhi—and other cities like it—can move towards becoming healthier, more inclusive, and genuinely sustainable places to live.

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Annexure

Survey questionnaire is as follows:

Perceptions of Sustainable Urban Design in Delhi

- **Demographic Information**

- 1) Name
- 2) Age Group
- 3) Gender
- 4) Occupation
- 5) Area of Residence, if living in Delhi
 - a. Central Delhi
 - b. East Delhi
 - c. New Delhi
 - d. North Delhi
 - e. North East Delhi
 - f. North West Delhi
 - g. Shahdara
 - h. South Delhi
 - i. South East Delhi
 - j. South West Delhi
 - k. West Delhi
 - l. NCR
- 6) If not a resident of Delhi, please specify region/state/country
- 7) How long have you been a resident of Delhi? (In case of temporary residence, please select duration of visit)

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- a. Less than 6 months
- b. 6 months - 1 year
- c. 1-3 years
- d. 3-5 years
- e. 5-10 years
- f. 10+ years

- **Awareness and Understanding of Sustainable Urban Design**

- 8) How familiar are you with the concept of “Sustainable Urban Design”?
- 9) Where did you first learn about sustainable urban design?
- 10) Have you observed any sustainable urban initiatives in Delhi? (e.g., green buildings, cycle tracks, electric buses, pedestrian zones, rooftop gardens)
- 11) Which sustainable features did you observe (if any)? Tick all that apply.
 - a. Electric buses/public transport
 - b. Pedestrian-friendly zones
 - c. Waste segregation systems
 - d. Bicycle lanes
 - e. Water conservation measures
 - f. Renewable energy (e.g., solar panels)
 - g. None

- **Perception of Current Urban Design Practices in Delhi**

- 12) How would you rate the current quality of urban spaces in Delhi? (roads, green spaces, pedestrian facilities)
- 13) Do you think Delhi’s urban design currently prioritizes sustainability (green cover, walkability, low emissions)?
- 14) Do you find such initiatives accessible and inclusive for all sections of society?
- 15) How practical do you think sustainable urban design practices are in the context of Delhi?
- 16) Have sustainable initiatives (parks, recycling, green transport) impacted your daily life? If yes, how?
- 17) Which sustainable features do you think Delhi needs the most? Tick all that apply.
 - a. More green spaces and urban forests
 - b. Improved pedestrian and cycling infrastructure
 - c. Pollution reduction (air/water)
 - d. Heat-resilient infrastructure (cool roofs, shading)
 - e. Better public transport (electric buses, metro integration)
 - f. Waste management and recycling initiatives
- 18) What challenges do you think Delhi faces in implementing sustainable urban design?
 - a. Lack of public awareness
 - b. Government policies/funding issues
 - c. Space constraints
 - d. Public resistance to behavioural changes
 - e. Maintenance and enforcement problems
- 19) Have sustainable initiatives (e.g., green drives, pedestrian zones, electric buses) improved your daily life in Delhi?
 - a. Yes, significantly
 - b. Somewhat
 - c. Not much impact
 - d. No impact at all
- 20) Do you face any inconveniences due to such initiatives (e.g., restricted vehicle zones, construction delays)?

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- 21) Would you personally be willing to support sustainable initiatives (e.g., use public transport, reduce waste, plant trees)?
 - a. Yes, definitely
 - b. Maybe, depending on convenience
 - c. No
- 22) Any suggestions on improving the practicality and public acceptance of sustainable urban design in Delhi?